

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE PROVISIONS OF THE CONSTITUTION OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA, 1999 (AS AMENDED) RELATING TO APPLICATION OF ISLAMIC LAW IN SHARIAH COURTS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This article, critically, assesses the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) which relate to the application of Islamic Law in Shariah Courts in Nigeria. Before the coming of colonial masters in the territory, nowadays, called 'Nigeria' there were rules of Islamic law applicable in shari'a Courts in the Sokoto Caliphate. The British Colonialists mixed their laws for the purpose of application in the then Alkali Courts alongside Islamic Law. In the year 2000, shari'ah was re-introduced in some Northern States. Coincidentally, Nigeria returned to Democratic System of Governance paving the way for a new Constitution. Some of the major problems giving rise to this research work are that there is an intense controversy as to the conformity of the provisions of the Constitution relating to the application of Islamic Law in Shari'a Courts in the country with the principles of Islamic law and the sufficiency of same to regulate shari'ah in the in Nigeria. Codification of offences as a prerequisite for application, concepts of pardon, nolle prosequi, appointment of more than one judge to man sharia court, cross-examination of witnesses as oppose impeachment are considered alien in Islamic Law. The main objectives of this article are to critically assess the extent to which such provisions are in consonance with the Shariah and the sufficiency of same to regulate it in Nigeria. The methodology employed in the conduct of this research is doctrinal. Primary and secondary sources housed in libraries and internet were consulted. It is observed that to a very large extent, the provisions of the Constitution relating to Sharia are not in line with the principle of Islamic Law and are not sufficient to regulate same. It is recommended that these provisions should be amended to bring same to tally with the principles of Shariah to fill in the gaps left.*

1.1 Introduction

This article, critically, assesses the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of

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Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) which relate to the application of Islamic Law in *Shariah* Courts in Nigeria. Specifically, therefore, the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) relating to *Shari'ah* would be critically assessed with a view to establishing the extent to which they are in tune with the principles of Islamic Law as well as their adequacy or otherwise to regulate *Shari'ah* in Nigeria. Provisions of the Constitution relating to powers of a Governor and the President to pardon convicted criminal by the *Sharia* Courts, powers of the Attorneys-General of the Federation and the State to takeover, discontinue, terminate criminal cases before *Sharia* courts, appointment of more than one Judge to man *Sharia* Court, cross-examination and re-examination of witnesses, abolishment of slave trade and slavery, jurisdiction of the *Shariah* Court of Appeal of a State, qualifications for appointments into the offices of a Grand *Kadis* and *Kadis* of *Shariah* Court of Appeal would be critically assessed. These would be followed by conclusion, which comprises of the observation, recommendations and concluding remarks.

1.2 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria is the Supreme law of the land. There have been series of Constitutions in Nigeria. But

the Current Constitution is the one enacted on the 29th of May, 1999. It is the Constitution that establishes the basic structures of Nigerian Government at various levels. Specifically speaking, the Constitution establishes the judicature and legislature at the Federal and State levels.¹

1.3 Establishment and Constitution of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal of the State

The Constitution establishes the *Shariah* Court of Appeal in the state that requires same.² It further provides for the establishment of other courts and applicable laws and procedures before them by the State Houses of Assembly. In its furtherance to regulate Islamic law at the state level, it provides for the constitution of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal of a state pursuant to which the Sokoto State *Sharia* Court of Appeal was established. The sections provide as follows: The *Sharia* Court of Appeal of the State shall consist of

- (a) a Grand Kadi of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal; and
- (b) such number of *Kadis* of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal
- (c) as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly

of the state³

In addition, Section 278 of the same document provides for the number of *Kadis* duly constituting the *Sharia* Court of Appeal which

¹ *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)* SS 47, 90 and 230.

² *Ibid*, SS 261 (1).and 275(1).

³ *Ibid*, S 275 (1) (a-b).

must consist of at least three *Kadis* of that court. This provision provides for the appointment of more than one *Kadi* to preside over a matter which the court has jurisdiction to entertain. The question that begs for answer is that 'is it in conformity with the rules of Islamic Law for a court to be manned by more than one judge on a matter before it'? The position of Islamic law is that jurists are unanimous on the issue of a number of judges to adjudicate on a single matter whether on appeal or a court of first instance. Thus, it is not allowed for more than one judge to sit on one case and in all cases, at a time under Islamic Law.⁴ The only situation where at least, and not more or less than two judges (if they can be called judges at all) are allowed to decide a case at a time is cases relating to a pilgrim who intentionally killed an animal in *Haram* and *Ithram* while performing pilgrimage. Authority for this can be gathered from the verse of the Glorious Qur'an, where Allah, the Most High, says:

“O you who believe kill not game while in the Sacred precincts or in the state of pilgrimage. If any of you does so intentionally, the Compensation is an offering, brought to the Ka'aba, of a domestic Animal equivalent to the one killed. As adjudged by two just men

Among you; or by way of atonement, the feeding of the indigent; or its equivalent in fast; That he may taste of the penalty of his deed. Allah forgives what is past: For repetition Allah will punish him for Allah is exalted, and Lord of retribution.⁵”

With this, one can safely assert that this constitutional provision is not in line with principles of Islamic Law but that of the Received English laws. This is dealt with extensively in the heading appraising the *Sharia Court Law, 2000* of Sokoto State under this chapter.

1.4 Qualifications for Appointment into the Offices of Grand *Kadi* and *Kadis* of the *Sharia Court of Appeal of the State*

The Constitution provides for the qualifications for appointment into the office of the *Kadi* of the *Sharia Court of Appeal*. In this regard, it has this to say:

A person shall not be qualified to hold office as a *Kadi*

- of the *Sharia Court of Appeal* of a state unless-
- he is a legal practitioner in Nigeria and has been so qualified for a period of not less than ten years and has obtained a recognized qualification in Islamic Law from an institution acceptable to the National Judicial Council; or*
 - he has attended and has obtained a recognized qualification in Islamic Law*

⁴ Aliyu Ibn Abdussalamu, *Al-Bahjah fi Sharh Al-Tuhfah* (Dar Al-Fikr, Egypt, 2nd Ed, 1951) p.19

⁵ Quran 5 v 95.

from the institution approved by the National Judicial Council and has held the qualification for a period of not less than ten years; and

(i) he either has considerable experience in the practice of Islamic

Law; or

(ii) he is a distinguished scholar of Islamic Law.⁶

From the above provisions, only educational qualifications are taken into consideration in appointment of persons into the office of the *Kadi* of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal. This is not enough to qualify a person for appointment into the office of a judge under Islamic Law. By this provision, once a person attained the said qualifications he is qualified to hold such office notwithstanding his moral background. Thus, a *fasiq*, fraudulent, non-pious person thief, wine drinker, among other morally bankrupt persons may be qualified to be appointed into the office of a *Kadi* of *Sharia* Court of Appeal of a state such as Sokoto State as long as they possessed the said educational qualifications envisaged by the Constitution. It goes without saying that the role of National Judicial Council, Judicial Service Commission, Department of State Service among other stakeholders in the appointment of judges is helpful in making sure that other qualifications not expressly stated in the Constitution are taken into consideration. However, the process has not

guaranteed the proper selection of judges beyond the stated qualifications in the legal document. This lacuna leaves much to be desired in regulating Islamic Law in Sokoto State taking into account the caliber of judges being appointed to man *Sharia* Courts. This will be discussed in details in the subsequent headings under this chapter.

1.5 Jurisdiction of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal of the State

The Constitution goes further to provide for the jurisdiction of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal of a state in a bid to regulate Islamic Law in the states that established same. In this respect, section 277(1) states as follows:

The *Sharia* Court of Appeal of a State shall, in addition to such other jurisdiction as may be conferred upon it by the law of the state, exercise such appellate and supervisory jurisdiction in civil proceedings involving questions of Islamic Personal

Law which the court is competent to decide in accordance with the provisions of subsection (2) of this section.

(2) for the purposes of subsection (1) of this section, the *Sharia* Court of Appeal shall be competent to decide any question of Islamic Personal Law regarding a marriage concluded in accordance with that law, including a question relating to the validity or dissolution of such marriage or a question that depends on such a

⁶ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) S 276(1) (2) (3) (a-b) (i-ii).

marriage and relating to family relationship or the guardianship of an infant;

(a) *where all the parties to the proceedings are Muslims, any question of Islamic Personal Law regarding marriage, including the validity or dissolution of that marriage, or regarding family relationship, a foundling or the guardianship of an infant;*

(b) *any question of Islamic personal law regarding a waqf, gift, will or succession where the endower, donor, testator or deceased person is a Muslim;*

(c) *any question of Islamic personal law regarding an infant, prodigal or person of unsound mind who is physically or mentally infirm.*⁷

This provision has divested the court of its jurisdiction to entertain criminal matters and some other civil matters such as matters relating to land, contracts concluded under Islamic law and landlord and tenant relationship created under Islamic Law. The provision has enjoyed a consistent endorsement of various courts in the country. Thus, in the case of *Alh Sa'idu Maje v Da'u Dillalin Shanu*,⁸ the Court of Appeal held that there is no gainsaying that the input of this section is clear and not nebulous at all. It therefore needs no interpretation other than the literal one. It should therefore serve as a guide to

Sharia Court of Appeal of the states and other courts such Area/*Shariah* Courts. It limited the jurisdiction of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal of the states to entertain and determine appeals file before them on criminal matters. This is, indeed, a fundamental lacuna in the Constitution in that Islamic Law encompasses all aspects of human endeavor which includes all categories of civil and criminal trials. The provision contradicts the provisions of section 36 of the same Constitution which guarantees the right to freedom of religion. Islamic law is only recognized where its total application is guaranteed without any form of restriction.

1.6 Abolishment of Slavery and Slave Trade

In compliance with the provisions of the Supplementary Convention of the United Nation Charter on abolishment of slavery and slave trade⁹, the Constitution provides for the abolishment of slavery and slave trade. It states that 'no person shall be held in slavery or servitude¹⁰.' This provision laid down the foundation upon which the Nigerian criminal law codes prohibit and punish slavery and slave trade.¹¹

Without doubt, rather than being in conformity with principles of Islamic Law, this provision is an attack on it with a view to rendering same

⁷ Ibid S 277 (1) (a-c).

⁸ CA/K/142/S/2005 (Unreported).

⁹ Supplementary Convention on the Abolishing of Slavery, the Slave Trade, and Institutions and Practice Similar to Slavery, 1957 in its preamble and Article 7 (a-c).

¹⁰ Ibid, S 34 (1) (b).

¹¹ Penal Code Law of Northern Nigeria, 1960, S 279. This section prohibits and punishes buying and disposing of slaves.

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toothless in that regard. There is no time in the history of Islamic law when slavery and slave trade are prohibited. Thus, it is a lacuna in any law as well as insufficiency on its part not to recognize such institution but rather prohibits and punishes same. There are a number of authorities under Islamic Law to the effect that the transactions relating to slavery and slave trade are legal and cannot be abrogated by any provision of the Constitution. The institution of slavery and slave trade remains intact under Islamic Law notwithstanding the provisions of the Constitution. Slaves were owned in all Islamic societies. They were owned in all Islamic societies both sedentary and nomadic, ranging from Arabia in the centre of North Africa in the West and to what is now Pakistan and Indonesia in the East.¹² Islamic states such as the Ottoman Empire, the Crimean Khanate and the Sokoto Caliphate must be termed slave societies because slaves there were very important numerically as well as a focus of the polities' energies.¹³ Many societies throughout the history have practiced slavery and Muslim societies were no exception.¹⁴

Therefore, Islamic Law and custom provided no basis for the abolishment of slavery or even for the curtailment of the slave trade. Although the

vast majority of contemporary Muslims abhor slavery, it still remains part of the Islamic religious laws.¹⁵ Thus, the verses of the Glorious Qur'an, traditions of the Noble Prophet peace be upon Him and the rules of Islamic Jurisprudence across the Four Sunni Schools and other are full of discussions on dealing with the slaves and their disposition. The approach of Islamic Law to slavery added the idea that freedom was the natural state of affairs for human beings and in line with, it limits the opportunity to enslave people, commends the freeing of slaves and regulates the way they are to be treated.¹⁶

In essence, Islam limits those who can be enslaved and under some circumstances. It treats slaves as human beings; it bans mistreatment of slaves. They are treated with kindness and compassion. It allows them to achieve their freedom and made same as virtuous act and finally bars Muslims from enslaving Muslims.¹⁷ Thus, the institution of slavery and slave trade is still obtainable and legal but only suspended for failure to allow the *sharia* to take its full pledges in an ideal Islamic State. The abolishment of this institution by the Constitution and other legal documents will not render same as prohibited under Islamic Law. This is subject of intense controversy among the

¹² Bernerd Lewis, *The Shaping of the Modern Middle East*, 1994 available at www.bbc.co.uk/religion visited on the 12/08/21 at 11:00am p43.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ Abdullahi Ahmed An-na'im, *Sharia and Basic Human Rights Concerns in Liberal Islam*, 1998, available at www.bbc.co.uk/religion visited on the 12/08/21 at 11:00am p46..

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

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contemporary scholars. To Gummi¹⁸, since an agreement was reached between the Western World leaders among other countries and African leaders on the abolishment of slavery and slave trade with an undertaking to make them independent, the practice stands abolished even under Islamic Law. Bauchi, countered that no amount of agreement can make illegal what has been made legal under the *Shariah*.¹⁹

But it should be pointed out that there are conditions to be fulfilled before slavery and slave trade are allowed under Islamic Law. There must be a valid jihad or war through which the slaves are acquired in form of prisoners of war. Thus, once legally acquired under the law, it is legal to sell or transfer same. They are not different from other valuables real and movables properties legally belonging to an individual or group. The authorities on these can be gathered from the verses of the Glorious Qur'an. Such as where it is decreed that it not permitted for a believer to kill a believer except mistakenly and when that happened the first alternative punishment or remedy is to free a Muslim female slave and the same remedy if is from the *dhimis* side. ²⁰ This is also dealt with in details in the subsequent headings.

1.7 Power of the Attorney-General of the State to Take Over or Discontinue Criminal Cases Instituted Before *Sharia* Courts

Additionally, the Constitution provides for the unrestricted power to the Attorney-General of a State, such as Sokoto State, to institute and undertake criminal proceedings against any person before any court of law in Nigeria other than a Court-martial in respect of any offence created by or under any law of the House of Assembly.²¹ It further confers power on the said Attorney-General of a State to take over and continue and discontinue at any stage of the proceedings before judgement such criminal proceedings instituted by any other authority or person.²² The law has been aptly settled and applied in the case of *State v Ilori*²³ that the Attorney-General is a law unto himself in taking decisions on matters under section 174 and 211 of the Constitution. His power is absolute and cannot be questioned or be reviewed. His discretion in exercising this power is absolute. He is under no control whatsoever, judicial or otherwise in relation to his powers of instituting or discontinuing criminal proceedings. There are a number of cases where the Attorney-General of Sokoto State took over and terminated criminal

¹⁸ Abubakar Mahmud Gummi, *Questions and Answers Session*, available at www.ikram.ng/ty, visited on 21/10/21 at 4:43pm p.41.

¹⁹ *Ibid*. Dahiru Uthman Bauchi countered Gummi that the concept of slavery and slave trade remains as it is under the sharia In that there is no revelation changing same.

²⁰ Qur'an Ch 4 v 92.

²¹ *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)*, S 211 (1) (a).

²² *Ibid*, S 211(1) (b-c).

²³ (1983) 2 S.C. 155/1 NSCC/69 (2001) FWLR (PT. 52) 281.

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proceedings instituted in the *Sharia* Courts. For instance, in the case of *NSCDC V Abubakar Usman*, the defendant is a businessman who deals in the business of selling beans at Kofar Gawo area of Sokoto State. He packed his sacks of beans and covered them with the nylon after the closure of the market and drove to home. One man called ‘Namaza’ and the other called ‘Dangarbe’ who work as labourers to one Abubakar Bello Kasarawa, the nominal complainant in the matter. These two people decided to uncover the beans packed by the defendant removed the nylon which they used in covering the goods belonging to the nominal complainant, their master. This conduct resulted in the missing of three (3) sacks of beans belonging to the defendant. The defendant now reported the matter to the Sokoto Central Market Police Station. The nominal complainant maneuvered his way at the police station and secured the release of the two men. The police refused to prosecute them. The nominal complainant now set the criminal law in motion by initiating action against the defendant that he stole a number of jericans of cooking oil. The Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corp Market division charged the defendant for the offence of theft at the Waje Lower *Shari’a* Court, Sokoto. The case was mentioned and the court remanded the defendant in Custodial Centre where he spent one day before he was granted bail by the court.

The defendant then filed a direct criminal complaint against the nominal complainant and the said two people in the court. On the day the case was slated for mention, the Attorney-General of Sokoto State took over the two cases from the earlier prosecutors.²⁴ There are indications that the Attorney-General is very interested in terminating the case against Abubakar Bello Kasarawa but finding it not easy due to the fact that the one against the defendant, Abubakar Usman has not been contemplated for being terminated.

From these provisions, the Attorney-General of Sokoto State has power to takeover and continue or terminate any criminal proceedings in any court in the state including *Sharia* Courts except a Court-martial. This is in direct conflict with the position of the law under Islamic Law. Once a criminal trial has begun in *Sharia* Court, it is not allowed for anybody, even the leader of the community to intervene by terminating same. The power to institute action or terminate same depends on the person who instituted it which also depends on whether it is the right of Allah, the Most-High, or the right of that person instituting the action.

1.8 Power of the President and Governor of a State to Pardon Persons Convicted by *Sharia* Courts

Similarly, the Constitution empowers the Governor of a State such as Sokoto State to grant

²⁴ *NSCDC V Abubakar Usman* W.I.S.C/172C/2022 (Unreported); *Abubakar Usman V Abubakar Bello Kasarawa*

CMC/GW/123/DC/2022; *C.O.P. V Yazid & 1 or USC/SK/CR/15/2021* (Unreported).

any person concerned with or convicted of any offence created by any law of a state a pardon, either free or subject to lawful conditions.²⁵ He or she may grant a respite to any person, either for an indefinite or for specified period of the execution of any punishment imposed on such person for any offence.²⁶ He or she, as a governor can validly go ahead to substitute a less severe form of punishment for any punishment imposed on him for any offence he or she has committed.²⁷ The whole or any part of any punishment imposed on any person for any offence he committed or any penalty or forfeiture may be remitted by the Governor. The only restriction imposed on the Governor in the exercise of this power of prerogative of mercy is that he has to consult the advisory council of the state constituted by same Governor whose members are, mainly, his loyalists.²⁸

Without doubt, these provisions do not tally with what is obtainable under the principles of Islamic law. In Islamic criminal justice, there is absolute application of the rule of law. Once it was established by a court of law that a person committed any offence, no matter how highly placed he or she may be, he must be punished in accordance with the prescribed punishment. No body, not even the leader of that community, is allowed to intervene by pardoning him or

substituting the prescribed punishment with a lesser or less severe punishment or remit the punishment whatsoever. Likewise, nobody has power to pardon any person concerned with any offence. Mere interference is not allowed talk more of pardoning. It was reported that a companion (*Zaid*) of the Prophet peace be upon Him was urged to pardon *Makhdhumiyyah* and angrily answered them that had it been that His daughter *Fadimah* may Allah be pleased with her committed theft He would have amputated her limbs.²⁹

1.9 Codification of Offences as a Prerequisite for Application in *Sharia* Courts

The Constitution prohibits conviction of a person of a criminal offence unless such offence is codified by defining it and has its punishment prescribed in a written law. In that regard, it provides as follows:

Subject as otherwise provided by this Constitution, a person shall not be convicted of a criminal offence unless that offence is defined and the penalty therefore prescribed in a written law; and in this subsection, a written law refers to an Act of the National Assembly or a law of a state, and subsidiary legislation or instrument under the provisions of a law.³⁰

²⁵ *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)* S 212 91) (a).

²⁶ *Ibid*, S 212 (1) (b).

²⁷ *Ibid*, S 212 (1) (c).

²⁸ *Ibid*, S 212 (1) (d).

²⁹ Salih Ibn Fauzan, *Commentary on Umdat Al-hkam*, available at www.amrkhaleed.net visited on 24/08/21 at 2:30pm p5.

³⁰ *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)*, S 36 (12).

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By implication, this provision prohibits trial and conviction of a person of criminal offences under Islamic law such as robbery, theft, wine drinking, apostasy, *qadhif*, adultery/fornication, intentional homicide and unintentional homicides among other *hudud* offences duly defined with prescribed punishment by the provisions of the Glorious *Qur'an* and traditions of the Noble Prophet (Peace Be Upon Him). The legal basis is drawn from this provision. Our Muslim Judges who found themselves at the Bench have consistently upheld this position. Justice Muhammad Bello suggested that the Constitution asserts its supremacy and provided a person should not be convicted for any *shariah* offence unless the legislature has passed it into law by way of codification. To him, application of criminal aspect of *shariah* without codification could be unconstitutional. He observed that *shariah*, as stated in the *Qur'an*, *Hadith* and other sources, is not 'written law' within the meaning of the above provision.³¹

This provision is not only in sharp conflict with the rules of Islamic law but sharply employed to undermine same. Under Islamic law, the better position of the law is that codification is not known to law. This is because the Supreme legislator is Allah, the All-Knowing. The requirement that law must be passed by either

the National Assembly or State House of Assembly before it can validly be used to convict an offender is, indeed, a transgression under Islamic law. Codification (*Taqnin*) purely hinders freedom of *ijtihad* which is the main reason for its prohibition under Islamic Law. It furthers narrow the scope, introduces practices not in accordance with rules of same.³²

It goes without saying that attempts in Islamic history have been made after the periods of the Prophet peace be upon Him, His companions and those who followed them under whose leadership the question of *taqnin* did not arise at all. With the passage of time, when a growing number of juristic schools appeared, the rulers themselves began to feel the necessity of codified law. This development was linked to the well-documented event of *Ibn al-Muqaffa's* dialogue with Caliph Abu *Ja'afar Al-Mansur*. *Muqaffa* was the first to see the necessity for codification which was rejected by the Caliph Mansur citing reasons that it hinders the freedom of *Ijtihad* enjoyed in the first three centuries of Islamic history.³³ That fruitless effort continued up to the period of *Harun Rashid* where *Imam Malik* vehemently rejected it.³⁴

Not only in the classical period, the question of codification was arisen among the contemporary scholars of Islamic Law. Nowadays, there are two

³¹ Hauwa Ibrahim, *Practicing Shariah Law* p23.

³² Najmaldeen K. Kareem Zanki, *Codification of Islamic Law Premises of History and Debates of Contemporary Muslim*

Scholars in International Journal of Humanities and Social Science (2018) 2, 113.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ *Ibid*, p.117.

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dominant opinions concerning the issue of codification of Islamic Law. The proponents of codification such as *Sheikh Ali Al-khallaf*, *Abu Zahrah*, *Ahmad Fahmi*, *Zaki Abdalbarr* among others are of the opinion that codification of Islamic Law became necessary and called for Arab countries to embrace it especially the Saudi Kingdom. Their reasons for this view are as follows:

1. It makes *Shari'ah* laws more attainable. It provides judges and jurists with a reference and rescues them from blindness. The Islamic jurisprudence contains a lot of disputes and arguments. If it is reduced to codes, it will surely help the judges and lawyers make recourse to them and comprehend the laws without any confusion or disturbance.
2. It may help Muslims filter and choose the most suitable opinions of jurists.
3. It is difficult today to have judges with qualifications to independently deduce the legal rules from the primary sources.
4. It may assist in unifying the judgements of the judges.
5. The Muslims may not be capable to achieve mastery and excellence without getting rid of the influence of foreign laws which were enforced upon them.³⁵

In contrast, the opponents of codification object this idea. The leading scholars of Saudi Arabia such as *Abu Zaid*, authored books addressing the

issue of codification and concluded that it is not applicable under Islamic Law insisting that the nature of its legislation refutes codification and its adoption by Muslims is maladjusted and inappropriate.³⁶ They cited the following reasons for its rejection:

1. The fear of distorting the legal rules by the rulers via applying the codes as a device to realize their own interests.
2. Islamic legal rules have been implemented for more than fourteen centuries without official codes.
3. The Common Law system of several developed Western countries such as English Common Law, approves the fact that it is still acceptable to apply laws without being drafted in systematic codes.
4. It is opposed to the rights of free *ijtihad* granted to judges and qualified scholars.³⁷

From the foregoing, it is believed that Islamic legal system follows neither the common or civil law approaches. The reason advanced by the proponents of codification that countries cannot do without influence of foreign law is not a valid reason. It confirms that foreign laws which are contrary to the provisions of *Shariah* are incorporated in it as canvassed by the opponents of it and evidenced in countries such as Nigeria. It was through same agenda that Common Law of England was imported into the country and made applicable even in Islamic Courts. The

³⁵ *Ibid*, p.118.

³⁶ *Ibid*.

³⁷ *Ibid*.

salaf rejected it based on their understanding of the sources of Islamic Law. They are better than those who came after them in terms of everything concerning Islamic Law. The further beauty of it is that they maintained the position of illegality of codification of it during the first three periods attested by the Prophet peace be upon Him as the best in terms of everything relating to Islam. It also stagnates and make rigid, the application of Islamic Law, particularly, Islamic criminal justice system.

1.10 Cross-Examination and Re-examination of Witnesses in Sharia Courts

The Constitution provides for the cross-examination of the prosecution witness by any person who is charged with a criminal offence. By this right, an accused has right to examine, in person, or his representative, the witnesses called by the prosecution before any court or tribunal.³⁸ The essence of this procedure is to discredit the evidence or testimony of the witness. It is done by way of confrontation among other methods with a view to making the witness contradicts himself even if he stated what he saw or heard transpired in the matter at hand. Once the testimony of a witness has been discredited via cross-examination, such evidence is not admissible and the party calling same shall not prove or disprove any fact.

However, under Islamic law, there is no provision for cross-examination of witnesses both under civil and criminal matters. What is obtainable under Islamic law is the impeachment of a witness by either of the parties to both civil and criminal proceedings. This is done by showing that the witness who testified against you is *fasiq* such as a liar, adulterer, not *adil*, or that there is blood relationship which disqualifies the witness from testifying such as father giving evidence in favour of his son or daughter or that there is hatred between the witness and who he is testifying against. Thus, this provision is in conflict with the rules of Islamic Law and such not sufficient to regulate civil and criminal trial in *Sharia* Court. This procedure is more just in accomplishing the end of justice. a witness is allowed to state the truth of what he saw or heard relating to particular case. Once he informed the court by way of testimony his evidence is admissible unless he is within the status whose evidence is not allowed under the law.

1.11 Right to Freedom of Religion

The Constitution legalises the serious offence of apostasy, *riddah*, where it provides as follows: Every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom either alone or in community with others, and in public or in private to manifest and

³⁸ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) S 36 (6) (d).

propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice and observance.³⁹

While one arm of the above provision, which provides that every person has the right to practice his religion is in line with the principles of Islamic Law, the other arm is in direct conflict with same. Allah says in the Glorious Qur'an, 'there is no compulsion in religion'⁴⁰. This is the arm of the section which provides for the right of a person to change his religion is offensive of the provisions of Islamic Law. The Prophet (Peace be Upon Him) is reported by Anas bin Malik to have said 'whoever changes his Islamic faith kill him (by way of *hadd*)'⁴¹

1.3 Conclusion

1.3.1 Observations

1.3.2 General Observations

The general observation from this research work is that a critical assessment of the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, (as amended) regarding Islamic Law, has exposed a very wide range of gaps in the said Provisions. As such, they are not sufficient to regulate *shariah* in the state. It further revealed that to some extent, many these provisions are not in line with the provisions or principles of Islamic Law. Therefore, the aims or purposes for which these set of provisions are meant to achieve in regulating the

implementation and application of Islamic Law in Nigeria are not sufficiently met. Additionally, most of these provisions are a carbon copy of Common Law Principles and Statutes of General Application as enforced in England as of 1900 which were later made applicable in Nigeria.

1.3.3 Specific Observations

Specifically, the observations made from this research work are as follows:

1. The concept of codification of Islamic Criminal Law before application in *Sharia* Courts as professes by the Constitution is not in line with the provisions of Islamic Law,
2. The constitution and quorum of *Sharia* Courts to be manned by more than one *Kadi* or Judge is not in tune with the dictates of Islamic Law.,
3. Qualifications for appointment of *Kadis*/Judges of *Sharia* Courts which centre only on educational qualifications and experience rather than consideration of other ethical issues are not in conformity with the principles of Islamic Law.
4. Ousting of criminal jurisdiction of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal and other civil matters such as land cases and contract concluded under Islamic Law by the provisions of the Constitution are not in conformity with the principles of

³⁹ *Ibid*, S 38 (1).

⁴⁰ Qur'an Ch 2 v .256; Isma'il ibn Kathir, *Tafsir Al-qur'an Al-Karim*, available at www.quran.ksu.edu.sa/tafse, visited on the 16/08/21 at 3:46pm p 42.

⁴¹ Al-Nas'I, *Sunan Al-Nasa'I*, available at www.qalargasulullah.com, visited on 16/08/21 at 4:00pm..

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Islamic Law and constitute insufficiency to regulate Islamic Law in Nigeria.

5. The concept of Attorney-General of the State with unquestionable and unrestricted powers to take over and discontinue criminal proceedings in any *Sharia* Court in the Nigeria or State, as the case may be,

6. Powers of the President and Governor to pardon persons convicted by the *Sharia* Courts in Nigeria, provisions for cross-examination and re-examination of witnesses in *Sharia* Courts rather than impeachment are alien to Islamic Law as such not in line with same.

1.3.4 Recommendations

1.3.5. General Recommendations

The following are the general and specific recommendations which will, at a very large extent, ensure the adequacy of the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 relating to Islamic Law, to regulate *shariah* in the state as well as ensuring conformity with same:

Generally, all the provisions of the Constitution relating to Islamic Law should be reviewed to make same in conformity with the principles of *shariah* and fill in the gaps left therein as well so as to guarantee protection of right to freedom of religion as provided therein...

1.3.6 Specific Recommendations

Specifically, it is hereby recommended that:

1. The requirements imposed by Section 36(12) of the Constitution relating to codification of Islamic Law before its validity for application

in *Sharia* Courts should be removed and abolished by deleting same and make the provisions to include any offence established by the primary and secondary sources of *shariah* rather than the ones enacted by a legislative house in that under Islamic Law Allah, the Most-High, is the Supreme Legislature. This will ensure the maintenance of freedom of *Ijtihad* which is hindered by application of codification. It will also limit the incorporation of alien laws and traditions in Islamic Laws to be applied in the *Shari'a* Courts in Nigeria.

2. Sections 278 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria making the quorum of the *Sharia* Court of Appeal and *Sharia* Courts in the state constituting more than one Kadi or Judge as the case may be should be reviewed and allow them to be constituted by only one Kadi Or Judge as the case may be at a sitting. This is more purely in line with principles of Islamic Law. If this is done, the law then goes ahead to increase the number of these courts in the state to tackle redundancy and ensure. Adequacy of same.

3. The provisions of section 276 (1)(2) (3) (a-b) (i-ii) of the Constitution relating to the qualifications for appointment of *Kadis* and Judges of the *Sharia* Courts should be reviewed to include ethical or moral qualifications in addition to the only educational qualifications and experience provided therein. This will fill the gaps left and ensure just and proper appointment expressly stated so that room for speculation is closed. This will no doubt ensure

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just, efficient and effective justice delivery in Nigeria

4. . The provisions of section 277(1) (a-c) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) should be reviewed by expanding same to confer the *Sharia* Court of Appeal with jurisdiction to entertain criminal matters and other civil matters such as dispute relating to land, contracts, recovery of premises and all other cases in that Islamic Law or Personal Law torches or cover all aspects of human endeavour. This will guarantee the freedom of religion as provided under the same Constitution for the Muslims in Nigeria. Or in the alternative, the Phrase ‘Personal Law’ should be deleted and replaced with the ‘Islamic Law.’

5. The provisions of sections 211(1)(a) of the Constitution as well as 212(1) (a) relating to powers conferred on the Governor to pardon persons convicted of an offence by *Sharia* Courts should be completely removed and abolished to guarantee the right to freedom of religion and make same in line with the principles of Islamic Law.

6. The powers conferred on the Attorney-General of the State to takeover or discontinue criminal proceedings initiated in *Sharia* Courts and the powers conferred on the Governor to pardon persons convicted by the *Sharia* Courts should be totally expunged in relation to *Sharia* Courts by way of exempting them from the application of the said provisions. The provisions of sections 36(6) (d) of the Constitution should

be reviewed by deleting the words ‘cross-examination’ and ‘re-examination’ and inserting the word ‘impeachment’ in the Constitution. This is the procedure of discrediting witnesses under Islamic Law. That is by impeachment not through cross-examination and re-examination. The jurisdiction of the *Sharia* Courts should be expanded and make provisions to cover cases relating to violation of copyrights (*huquq al-dab’i*) under Islamic Law by reviewing the *Constitution*. This is timely taking into consideration the ways and manners works of authors in Islamic Law are being reproduced and sold freely as well as tempered without remedies obtainable in the *Shari’a* Courts in Nigeria. Similarly, provisions should be made, particularly, under the Constitution to confer jurisdiction on *Sharia* Courts in Nigeria to entertain disputes regarding landlord and tenant relationship concluded under Islamic Law..These provisions should be reviewed to take into consideration, expressly, the admissibility or otherwise of the electrically, digitally or computer generated evidence such as a contract concluded digitally or electronically and the only evidence is in form of computer printout. This will maintain the nature of Islamic Law of being flexible to suit any time.

1.4 Concluding Remarks

An assessment of the above provisions of the Constitution has yielded a result to the effect that these provisions are in dare need of total overhaul so as to conform with the notion of civil

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and criminal justice in Nigeria. An interference with the smooth and unrestricted application of Islamic Law as it was during the period of the 18th Century Jihadists has been detected. The way and manner the British Colonial Administrators, the legal mechanisms they used to strangulate the smooth application of *shariah* is the same way and manner some other things that are not in line with it are inserted consciously or unconsciously, deliberately or otherwise. It is also the same manner as the colonialists excluded some provisions of *sharia* and made their application prohibited. The problems highlighted in these articles have been tackled, the aim and objectives achieved. The observations are made and recommendations are suggested. If implemented, the findings therein will assist, to a very large extent, in addressing the problems of inadequacy and conformity of the provisions of the Constitution assessed in regulation to Islamic Law in Nigeria. Some of the observations and recommendation in this article will look somehow to other scholars. In this regard, it should be noted that the work earlier intended to look at the positions of *shariah* no matter how strange a particular position may appear to some other scholars. The right to freedom of expression and one's religion is protected under the law. Other provisions that this article has not covered should also be taken into consideration by other interested researchers in the area.

The article recommends for further research in the area to further identify more gaps as contained in these provisions as well as other provisions that are not in consonance with the principles of *shariah* which this article falls short of. If this is done, one day, these provisions of the constitution to be applied in the *Sharia* Courts in Nigeria will be better in terms of adequacy and conformity with the rules of Islamic Law. With this, the country will revert back to its present territory as the Sokoto Caliphate as it was. The country will witness the proper protection of lives and property and a considerate reduction in crimes rate to the effect that the whole country will be where a woman, who is very week interns of everything, can freely move from one place to another and one town to another carrying a cascade of gold without any molestation as proclaimed by a British Explorer, Hugh Clapperton, visiting the territory during the reign of Sultan Muhammad Bello.

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